

NATIONAL POLICY, INDUSTRY SITUATION AND MANAGEMENT MECHANISM INFLUENCING SUCCESSFUL MANAGEMENT MODE OF DANCESPORT EVENT IN CHINA

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Abstract

This study is based on the sports dance project in China for more than 30 years. Sports dance is a new competitive sport in China in recent years, which is deeply loved by the masses of the people. In the rapid development and growth in these ten years, it has become an emerging force that cannot be ignored in the development of competitive sports in China. But on the construction of sports dance event system is still in a chaotic disorder, various association, not for the development of the whole sports dance competition to do a unified planning and unified standards, event name, the function between all kinds of events is not obvious, visible, the sports dance sports extremely competitive line research analysis, improve the event system is the current social demand and the needs of the project development. We will discuss the relationship between national policies, event management and industry status and the dance sport event model. This study conducts an exploratory qualitative and quantitative study on the management of dance sport events in China. Based on the current situation of the management model of dance sport events in China, we try to establish a new event management model and management mechanism. Descriptive statistics were conducted to analyze the basic information of the respondents, and the reliability and validity tests of the survey data results showed that the correlation between the analysis items was good, which also showed that the reliability level was good. The data of this questionnaire are of high quality and reliability and can be used for further analysis. Subsequently, a confirmatory factor analysis of the three influencing factors of "national policy", "management mode" and "industry development" was conducted. This study investigated the fit degree of the model. The results showed that all the goodness of fit indicators met the general standard and the model fit well. The combined reliability (CR) is also performed, and the results show that the questionnaire structure model has good convergence efficiency. The discriminatory validity tests were also performed for independent and stress variable variables, and the model showed good discriminative validity. However, the prethreshold analysis showed a positive correlation between each dimension. Further analysis in the structural equation model (SEM) shows that reliability, convergence validity and differential validity of the dimensions and factors in this study have reached an acceptable level. On the basis of the measurement, a structural equation model is established based on the theoretical model research. Finally, for the fit of the overall model, both absolute, incremental or parsimonious fits reach an acceptable range, which shows that the overall fit of the theoretical model in this study is good. Finally, I give reasonable opinions, hoping to have some constructive suggestions for the development of Chinese dance sport events, and some ideas and assumptions about the management mode of Chinese dance sport events can be reflected in the implementation system.

Keywords: National Policy, Industry Situation, Management, Dance sport Event.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Statement and significance of the problem

At present, there are two international dancesport organizations internationally.(WDDSC / WORLD DANCE AND dancesport COUNCIL) The World Council for Dance and dancesport. It was established on September 22, 1950 in Edinburgh, Scotland, UK, and has 52 member associations registered in London, UK. (IDSF / INTERNATIONAL dancesport FEDERATION) International dancesport Federation. Founded in Prague in 1935, it has 79 member associations registered in Lausanne, Switzerland (International Olympic Committee, 1997). China dancesport federation after joining the international dancesport federation, officially held in Shanghai in November 2002, October 18-19, 2003 held in Wuxi China Asia Pacific dancesport championship, November 6-7, 2004 in Shanghai, China IDSF world youth standard dance championship and China Shanghai dancesport open, this is the first time in our country the world championships, and in recent years the international events is numerous.

There are some problems in China, such as unclear positioning, imperfect competition system construction and management .It mainly includes :domestic professional events are chaotic, and have obvious factions, which are relatively isolated, lack of connection, and do not form a unified whole .The construction of the competition chain is not perfect and disjointed from each other .It is only more than 30 years since the establishment of Chinese dancesport events . The event has a short history and the management is immature .In addition, because China pays more attention to learning foreign advanced technical and tactical theories and ignores the important position of dancesport events in China, it leads to the lack of high-end talents with rich theoretical knowledge of event management and experience in event operation .In addition, the competition market is not mature, there is no profit model in line with the characteristics of market operation, and the explicit value of market benefits is forgotten and shelved .The successful holding of the excellent dancesport event is the best way to actively explore the profit of the event operation. By holding excellent dancesport events, we can obtain huge economic benefits and promote the sustainable and healthy development of the events.

However, at present, the profit situation of China is still not optimistic, and even appear interest stratification, draw faction and other misconduct phenomenon.Yes, the fundamental reason is that the degree of marketization and commercialization is not enough .However, judging from the past experience, it is not difficult to see that the future development of Chinese dancesport events will keep up with the world trend, and the professionalization and globalization of the events will be the key and inevitable history of the evolution of the whole dancesport event.The author suggests that starting from the current situation of dancesport competition, the rules and competition system of dancesport competition should be standardized, the referees of dancesport competition should be screened to strive for" professionalism ,"and the market operation mode of dancesport competition should be optimized .In order to obtain more constructive theories and data ,the author tries to explore the factors affecting the development of Chinese dancesport events and tries to establish a new model through combing the management status of China, combining with the experience and model of experts and event operators.

1.2 Research questions

1. What is the current situation of Dancesport event management mode in China?
2. What factors are affecting the successful management mode model of Dancesport events in China?
3. How to create a successful management mode model for Dancesport events in China?

1.3 Study Objectives

1. To study the current situation of Dancesport event management mode in China.
2. To analyze the factors affecting the successful management mode model of Dancesport events in China.
3. To create a successful management mode model for Dancesport events in China.

1.4 Significance of this study

1. Provide reference and guidance for the development of Chinese dancesport event management mode.
2. Explore the factors affecting the development of the management mode of Chinese dancesport events, which is conducive to creating high-quality dancesport events, and then expand and improve the dancesport industry chain, and cultivate and explore the dancesport market.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Documents related to the management mode of dancesport events in China

This study focuses on the factors influencing the management model of dancesport events in China .Study the core concepts ,relevant information, theoretical basis and related research before conducting the research .On the basis of relevant concepts, theories and research and related research, the conceptual framework of research is established and applied to research operations. The investigators will describe each question in detail:

Factor Researchers /Year	National policy	Operation mechanism of the event	The industry itself	Event system	The impact of the event	Host city
1. Wang(2016).	√	√	√	√		
2. Sun.(2013).	√	√	√	√		
3. Lv(2021).		√	√	√		
4. Ye,Wang(2020).		√	√	√	√	
5. Zuo(2019) .	√	√	√	√		√
6. Li(2017).		√	√	√	√	√
7. Wu(2017).	√	√	√	√	√	√
8. Xue(2016).		√	√	√	√	√
9. Tong(2015).	√	√	√	√	√	√

10. Chen(2013).	√	√	√	√	√	
11. Zhu(2013).	√	√	√	√		
12. Wang(2009).			√	√		√
13. Xu(2007).	√		√	√		
14. Zhao(2005).	√		√	√		
15. Zhao(2003).			√	√		
Total	9	11	15	15	6	6

On the basis of related research results "national policy" ,"operation mechanism" ,"industry problem "and "system "is an important factor affecting the Chinese dancesport event management, so from the" event system "and" industry problems ,"to rebuild the new Chinese dancesport event management model is particularly key.

2.2 The conceptual framework of the study

In this study, through the large amount of literature and expert interviews, the current situation of China dancesport event management are analyzed and the influencing factors affecting the development of China dancesport event are summarized, the new China dancesport event management model is created, and the new model of China dancesport event is verified by the expert panel.

2.2.1 Current China dancesport event management model

Table 1: Management model of China dancesport events

2.2.2. Suppose that the final Chinese dancesport event management model is established

At the present, the management mode of dancesport events in China is mainly divided into three systems :sports system, education system and social system .In the event system, the sports system and the education system are uniformly planned in the competitive system .Such

a tournament track is not clear enough, the hierarchy is not clear enough, the advanced order is chaotic and cannot meet the selection needs of all the track to enter the national team.

Table 2: Suppose China dancesport event management model

The ideal competition system in China should be a competition management mode with clear track, clear hierarchy, orderly order and "all things are possible" (Table 5). The so-called possibility means that every system and every track can be "selected for the national team," which is in line with the guidelines of sports for all and people's longing and yearning for a better life.

2.2.3 The Model of Chinese dancesport Event Management Organization

Table 3: China dancesport event management organization model

Under the promotion of the reform of market economic system, the current situation of dancesport competition management in China is a "center + association" jointly participated by the management of China Social Sports Guidance Center and China dancesport Federation. However, due to the current situation of non-Olympic sports in China, it cannot enjoy direct appropriations from the state, and in view of the non-profit nature of dancesport association, the competition funds can only be raised from the society or the people, and it does not have the ability to deal with economic affairs in law. With the deepening of the political and economic reform, the reform of the sports management system will eventually adapt to the needs of the industrial management of competitive sports, and will form a networked industrial management system.

At present, the organization structure of competition in China cannot meet the development needs of dancesport competition in China. Therefore, in terms of organizational structure, we should make it flat and adopt a functional structure for management, so as to improve the efficiency of information transmission and the resilience of organizational functions. After literature review and research inference, for the construction of dancesport industrialization organization and business model I think the ideal construction mode should be "center + association + club + company" model (table 6), namely in the state general administration of sports and under the authorization of the dancesport association and each club in the process of dancesport market management, set up a non-profit "China dance alliance", responsible for the organization and management of dancesport competition and market operation, coordinate the clubs, between economic interests or affairs. The highest authority of the China dancesport Union is the board of directors of the dancesport Union, which is composed of the managers or agents of the China dancesport Association and various clubs and sports teams, and the directors meet regularly every year. The board of directors of the company has the decision-making power, and the relevant matters of the company shall be reported by the general manager at the general meeting and solicit opinions from other directors and members. Once the relevant affairs of the company are approved by the board of directors, any member shall unconditionally abide by and execute them.

"China dancesport Alliance" belongs to the dancesport Association and belongs to the unified leadership of the superior center, but in terms of legal nature, it is a corporate attribute with independent legal person status. Although under the macro leadership of the superior association or the center, but in dealing with economic affairs, it will not be intervened by the superior. Such organization structure mode, not only avoid the dancesport association in the inconvenience, but also from the reality of socialism in our characteristics, break through the existing organizational structure, make our country dancesport competition gradually formed to adapt to the market economy system of intensive industrialization economic entities.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study on the influencing factors of dancesport event management mode in China is a mixed method study, namely qualitative and quantitative research. In order to conduct the study according to the study objectives, the investigators identified the study process, study

population and samples, study tools, data collection and data analysis .The specific contents are as follows:

3.1 Process of conducting research

According to the research methods and objectives, the researchers defined the research process as the following three steps :

Step 1: Study the current situation of the management mode of dancesport events in China through literature analysis and expert interviews.

Step 2: Analyze the factors affecting the development of the management mode of Chinese dancesport events .By analyzing the opinions of the survey subjects, the factors affecting the development of Chinese dancesport event management mode are found out.

Step 3: Develop a new model of Chinese dancesport event management mode.

3.2 Population and samples

3.2.1 Population

The survey factors affecting the development of the management mode of dancesport events in China can be divided into three categories 1900 .1 :spectators who have watched the dancesport events and 2000 students majoring in dancesport; 2 100 .experts, professors and event managers who study dancesport events and dancesport industry, with a total of 4000 people.

3.2.2 Sample

The sample group was used to study the factors influencing the development of dancesport events in China .Sample size was determined by Craig C's table and Morgan) Krejcie & Morgan, 1970, p .(608.The sample size consists of three parts .1 :Of 190 spectators; 2 200 .contestants; and 10 experts, professors and event managers in the dance port industry. A total of 400 people.

3.2.3 Research Tools

The tool used in this study was a questionnaire used to investigate the factors influencing the development of dancesport event management models in China .The questionnaire is divided into two parts:

The first part :the questionnaire about the general situation of the respondents, that is, the educational background, position, experience, etc ,.are closed questions, a total of 7 items.

Part II :Questionnaire on influencing factors of management mode in China .Through the analysis of relevant literature, the researchers collected and sorted out the factors affecting the development of Chinese dancesport event management mode, and compiled the Questionnaire on the Factors influencing the Development of Chinese dancesport Event Management Mode . The questionnaire was classified according to the subitems / indicators of the closed questions .

The questionnaire used the 5-level quality type of the Likert scale, and the researchers set the score to 5 grades.

3.2.4 Data collection

- 1) The Graduate School sent out questionnaires to 4 sampling teams, asking them to submit questionnaires on the factors affecting the development of dancesport events in China.
- 2) Send questionnaires about the factors affecting the development of Chinese dancesport events to the 4 sample groups .Note" to the investigator "on the envelope to facilitate responses.

4. RESULT AND FINDINGS

4.1 Questionnaire survey results

4.1.1 Reliability analysis

Reliability analysis, also known as "reliability analysis," is the test of the stability, consistency and reliability of the measurement results. In order to ensure the accuracy of the measurement, reliability analysis of the valid data in the questionnaire is needed. At present, the "Cronbach" coefficient is mainly used to illustrate the analysis in social science research: In general, if the reliability coefficient is above 0.9, it means that the reliability is good, if it is between 0.8 and 0.9, it means that the reliability is good, if it is between 0.7 and 0.8, it means that the reliability is good, if it is between 0.6 and 0.7, it means that the reliability is acceptable, if it is below 0.6, it means that it needs to be revised. The results are in the table below.

It can be seen from Table 4.1 that the reliability coefficients of each dimension are high, which indicates that the reliability of the research data is of high quality. As for "Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted," after any item is deleted, the reliability coefficient of other items will not be significantly improved, which means that this item should not be deleted. As for "Corrected item-total Correlation," that is, CITC value, "the CITC value of each analysis item is greater than 0.4, indicating that the correlation of each analysis item is good, and the reliability level is good. To sum up, the data of the questionnaire in this study is of high quality and reliability, which can be used for further analysis.

4.1.2 Validity analysis

Validity refers to the degree to which the psychological and behavioral characteristics to be measured can be accurately measured by the test or scaling tool, that is, the accuracy and reliability of the test results. In general, the smaller the significance level $P(0.05 >)$ of the Bartlett sphericity test, the more likely there is to be a meaningful relationship between the original variables. The KMO value is used for the simple correlation coefficient and partial correlation coefficient between the comparison terms, and the value is between 0 and 1. The criteria of whether it is suitable for factor analysis are: more than 0.9 is very suitable, 0.9-0.7 is suitable; 0.7-0.6 is appropriate; 0.6-0.5 is not suitable; Give up below 0.5. Bartlett sphericity test values were used to test whether the correlation coefficients between items were

significant .If the significance was less than 0. ,05it indicated that each item was suitable for factor analysis.

Table 4.2: Validity analysis table

Variable	KMO	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity		
		Chi-Square	df	p
National policy	0.960	6,819.017	190	0.000
Management mechanism	0.957	6,958.708	190	0.000
Industry situation	0.960	6,959.112	190	0.000
Dancesport event management	0.702	318.178	3	0.000

Validity was verified using KMO and Bartlett tests .As can be seen from Table4 . ,each variable has a KMO value greater than 0 .7.The research data is very suitable for information extraction) it is very effective from the side (and can be used for factor analysis.

4.2 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

4.2.1 Confirmatory factor analysis of National policy

Figure 4.1: Confirmatory factor analysis diagram of National policy

According to structural equation modeling theory, it is a complicated problem to evaluate the fit degree of a model. When evaluating the model, different fitting indexes have different evaluation priorities. Therefore, it is generally believed that the quality of a model should be comprehensively evaluated by multiple indicators rather than one indicator. This study investigated the fitting degree of the model, which mainly involved three indexes: absolute fitting index, relative fitting index and reduced fitting index. The absolute fitting indexes used are the Chi-square degree of freedom ratio) CMIN/DF, (the square root of the approximation error) RMSEA, (and the goodness deviation index (GFI). (The relative fit indexes are increasing fit index) IFI (and comparative fit, respectively. Reduced fit index) CFI, (relative fit index) RFI, (gauge fit index) NFI (and reduced fit index are all reduced norm fit index) PNFI. (See Table 4. 3for details.

Table 4.3: Fitting value table of National policy

index	Judgment criteria	Statistical value	Fitting situation
CMIN	-	336.574	-
DF	-	166	-
CMIN/DF	<3	2.028	yes
RMSEA	<0.08	0.051	yes
GFI	>0.90	0.925	yes
IFI	>0.90	0.975	yes
CFI	>0.90	0.975	yes
RFI	>0.90	0.945	yes
NFI	>0.90	0.952	yes
PNFI	>0.50	0.831	yes

As can be seen from Table 4. 3, CMIN/DF value is 2. 028 which is less than 3. The RMSEA was 0. 051 which was lower than the standard level 0. 08 indicating a good fit. GFI value of 0. 925 IFI value of 0. 975 CFI value of 0. 975 RFI value of 0. 945 NFI value of 0. 952 all meet the standard of excellence, and PNFI value of 0. 831 that is, greater than 0. 5. All indexes of goodness of fit were in line with the above general standards, and the model was well fitted.

Combinatorial reliability) CR (is one of the criteria for judging the intrinsic quality of a model, reflecting whether all items in each potential variable consistently explain the potential variable. A CR greater than 0. 7 indicates that all terms of each potential variable consistently explain the potential variable. The convergent validity of each dimension is reflected in the mean variance extraction) AVE, (whose value is usually used to reflect the convergent validity of the scale, which can directly show how much variation is explained by the underlying variable from the measurement error, so that the larger the value, the greater the percentage of variation. The less the relative measurement error is explained by the underlying variable. Typically, this value is required to be above 0. 5. It can be seen from Table 4. 4 that all AVE values are greater than 0. 5 and all CR values are greater than 0. 7. The results show that the questionnaire structure model has good convergence and effectiveness.

4.3 Structural Equation Model (SEM)

The results show that the reliability, convergence validity and differential validity of each dimension and factor in this study have reached an acceptable level .On the basis of measurement, a structural equation model is established according to the study of theoretical model .Regarding the evaluation of model fit, according to Bagozzi and Yi ,(1988) it is the evaluation of the evaluation model from the preliminary fitting criteria: the preliminary fitting criteria evaluate the internal structure of the overall model (1 .Basic fit criteria :This standard is used to detect problems and input errors that can be identified by the model .It requires that the error of the measurement index cannot be negative, and the factor load must be between 0. .0.95-5As shown in Table 4. ,5the factor load of each structural index in this study is above 0 ,5.and the measurement error is not negative .Overall, this model is in the acceptable range.

Table 4.6: Model fitting table

index	Judgment criteria	Statistical value	Fitting situation
CMIN	-	2465.431	-
DF	-	1872	-
CMIN/DF	<3	1.317	yes
RMSEA	<0.08	0.028	yes
GFI	>0.90	0.841	acceptable
IFI	>0.90	0.973	yes
CFI	>0.90	0.973	yes
RFI	>0.90	0.891	acceptable
NFI	>0.90	0.896	acceptable
PNFI	>0.50	0.859	acceptable

As can be seen from Table4 . ,6the CMIN/DF value is 1. ,317which is less than 3. RMSEA was 0. ,028less than the standard level of 0. ,08indicating good adaptability .GFI value is 0. ,841 IFI value is 0. ,973CFI value is 0. ,973RFI value is 0. ,891NFI value is 0. ,896all of which reach the acceptable range .PNFI value is 0. ,859greater than 0. .5All the indexes of goodness of fit reached the acceptable range, and the model fit well.

Table 4.7: Table of model path coefficients

Path	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Std.Estimate
National_policy→Management_mechanism	0.117	0.039	3.022	0.003	0.141
Industry_situation→Management_mechanism	0.609	0.059	10.385	***	0.726
Management_mechanism→Dancesport_event_management	0.211	0.083	2.555	0.011	0.222
National_policy→Dancesport_event_management	0.378	0.046	8.158	***	0.477
Industry_situation→Dancesport_event_management	0.229	0.068	3.346	***	0.287

As can be seen from Table 4.7, if $P > .05$, then the path is significant; when the path is significant, the coefficient is positive, and the independent variable of the path has a significant positive impact on the dependent variable. As can be seen from the above table, the p-value of all paths is less than 0.05, which means that all paths of the model are valid.

Table 4.8: Intermediary analysis table

path	Effect type	Estimate	Lower	Upper	P
National_policy → Management_mechanism → Dancesport_event_management	direct	0.477	0.389	0.566	0.000
	Indirect	0.031	0.005	0.067	0.015
	Total	0.508	0.420	0.596	0.000
Industry_situation → Management_mechanism → Dancesport_event_management	direct	0.287	0.094	0.462	0.003
	Indirect	0.161	0.040	0.309	0.011
	Total	0.448	0.337	0.550	0.000

Finally, the intermediate effect was tested, the Bootstrap method was used to sample 5000 times, and the confidence interval was 95% for analysis. As can be seen from the following table, the significance of the total effect, direct effect and indirect effect of each path was less than 0.05 and 95%CI did not include 0, indicating that all paths were significantly established. Therefore, it can be seen that the intermediary variable Management_mechanism plays a partial mediating role in the role of independent variables National_policy and Industry_situation on the dependent variable Dancesport_event_management.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Research summary

The development of the management mode of Chinese Dancesport events cannot be separated from the support of national policies. Of course, the project is still a "non-Olympic" project for the time being, so there is still room for the support of the national policy, which is also the goal of our sports dance industry practitioners - the success of the Olympic bid. Secondly, the optimization of the event management mode and the control of the industry development are also imminent. The following points are summarized specifically:

5.1.1. This paper makes a systematic analysis of the history and future of Chinese Dancesport competition, and divides the process of Chinese Dancesport competition into three stages: the budding period of communication and entertainment, the growth period and the growth period of all-round development. The development of dancesport competition began in the 1990s, and gradually popularized throughout the country with the development of dancesport. In the course of nearly 30 years of competition development, China's sports dance competition has from scratch, from scattered to concrete, systematic. However, the research of this paper is just a forced needle in the bottleneck or painful period of this period. I hope that the practitioners, experts and officials of the sports dance industry can re-examine the development status of our industry, management system mode and how to make new breakthroughs in policy.

5.1.2 At present, the current situation of sports dance events in China is mainly composed of three "brand" events, national Open Championship and youth Championship, as well as club league, fitness ballroom dance championships and other related events. Latin dance and modern dance include the main system of sports competition: sports system, education system and social system. The longitudinal structure of the competition organization system in China is composed of the old stage, the adult stage and the youth stage in China, which is divided into China Sports Dance Association as the core, and the educational association of China Sports Association as the core. There are various forms of associations under the two associations and in each region, which also greatly increases the difficulty of industry management and standardization. However, the organization of sports dance competition in China adopts the "enterprise" organization structure to allocate the authority.

5.1.3 Dancesport event system refers to a whole dancesport event system in dancesport competition, which is connected and complementary according to a certain order. The goal of China's dancesport system is to build an innovative and diversified dancesport system with Chinese characteristics, system norms, people-oriented, resource sharing and sustainable development. Although the development of sports dance competition in China changes with each passing day, the rapid development has also led to many disadvantages of competition. The main problems of the sports dance competition in China are: the overall level of the competition needs to be improved; the planning of the competition is unfavorable; the cultural understanding of the atmosphere of the competition; the current rules of the competition are not perfect; the professional ethics and business ability of the referees need to be improved; the management system of the competition, the lack of brand awareness and packaging awareness, and the intermediary company, which we need to solve.

5.1.4 Under the promotion of the reform of market economic system, the current situation of dancesport events in China is a social sports management system of "center + association" jointly managed by China Social Sports Guidance Center and China DanceSport Federation. However, because the dancesport association and the government do not have the legal ability to deal with economic affairs and other disadvantages. Sports dance industrialization organization and manage the most ideal construction mode should be "center + association + club + company" model, in the state general administration of sports and the center of the sports dance association and each club association, set up "China sports dance alliance" co., LTD., responsible for sports dance event management and market operation, and coordinate the economic interests between the clubs or affairs. It is an effective way for China to gradually form an intensive industrialized economic entity to adapt to China's market economic system. This is also the core idea and suggestion of this study, which may solve the current situation and shortcomings of the industry development chaos at the same time.

5.1.5 At present, the development of sports dance competition in China is not smooth, in the final analysis, because the rules and regulations are not perfect. The 91 edition of the DanceSport Competition Draft shall be revised or re-drafted with new competition rules, Develop the scoring criteria and specifications for each technical action, Quantitative scoring rules; Reorganize the competition and design items, Strictly control and check the registration

qualification of each group; While trying to change the existing ways of dancesport competition ,Gradually regulate the competition, Improve the watching experience of dancesport spectators and the judging quality of referees, Reduce the referee's referee error; In the future, when sports dance competitions are mature, Or consider" specialization "dancesport referees, Avoid coaches and referees " the same standard, training, examination, Having a dual identity " status quo .It is also one of the most volatile factors in our dancesport industry.

5.2 Research suggestion

5.2.1 The competent departments and associations of Dancesport competitions in China must pay attention to the modification of the rules of dancesport competitions in China, revise and improve the rules of competition as soon as possible according to the development of Dancesport in China, so as to ensure the development of dancesport competitions in China to adapt to the development of The Times faster.

5.2.2 Effectively supervise and modify the contents and methods of national sports dance referee training in China, and the training and assessment of referees should be carried out from the aspects of referee law, competition rules, adjudication skills ,professional ethics, etc . At the same time, for the" professionalization "of referees, we should start from improving the rewards of referees in sports dance competitions and eliminating the dual identity of referees and coaches.

5.2.3 Building the brand and platform of dancesport events, strengthening the industrialization and market operation of dancesport events, integrating competition resources, and exploring the "Internet "+ of dancesport competitions are the necessary ways to realize the diversified and sustainable development of dancesport competitions.

5.2.4 Gradually introduce the sports dance project into the education system, establish a good foundation for the campus sports dance, and improve the Chinese campus sports dance event system as soon as possible.

5.2.5 The objectives of the construction of China's dancesport competition system can be divided into short-term goals and medium-and long-term goals .Firstly, the short-term goals can be set in the following aspects .1 :Improve the open competition system, add municipal events in the open series; 2 .reform the club league, increase the district level in the club league; 3 .Reform the fitness ballroom competition system, change the fitness ballroom tournament into the open competition, and increase the community trials at the same time; 4 .Vigorously carry out the series of activities and events :establish the sports dance" league transition " competition system in the next stage of dancesport development .At the same time, the sports dance project will gradually penetrate into the education system, and the campus sports dance event system will be established .Through the discovery, selection and training of talents in multiple ways, the popularity, promotion and popularity of sports dance projects are comprehensively enhanced.

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